

I.FAST

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MILESTONE REPORT

Workshop on efficient magnet- and RF power supplies.

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ABSTRACT

All research infrastructures use power converters, and these can be more or less efficient. The importance of sustainability for many research infrastructures means that energy efficiency becomes a key factor during design and operations. As design methods evolve, better and better control of the output is offered, and higher efficiencies become available.

To discuss this, a workshop was organised at ESS in April 2024. The workshop focused on efficient power converters for magnets and RF sources and sustainability aspects for RIs.

I.FAST Consortium, 2024

For more information on IFAST, its partners and contributors please see <https://ifast-project.eu/>

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1 Introduction

All research infrastructures use power converters, and these can be more or less efficient. As design methods evolve, better and better control of the output is offered, and higher efficiencies become available. The importance of sustainability for many research infrastructures means that they are nowadays able to and asked to not only minimize losses but to also re-use lost energy (=heat) in a smart a way as possible, to produce part of the energy they use themselves, and to store energy, if possible.

A workshop was organized to highlight the different facets of sustainability, focused on efficient power converters for magnets and RF sources and sustainability aspects for Ris. Discussions concentrated on ways to improve efficiency for power converters and how facilities can tackle electrical supply, electrical production, and waste heat in innovative ways.

Many interesting discussions were held, and in general it was viewed that it is positive if sustainability is part of the planning for large RIs, but that adding sustainability aspects later in the life of a facility is certainly possible.

Figure 1: Group photo of the workshop participants "sustainable energy systems and accelerator research and development"

2 Program of the workshop

The workshop focused, as mentioned, on designs, strategy for energy supply, and sustainability. We tried to highlight how different facilities cope with the energy supply strategy and sustainability issues. There were several presentations on new and innovative designs for power converters/power sources. Control of power converters can be very precise using current digital tools. This benefits all, since the improved control normally can be accompanied by higher efficiency, and better control of for example RF generation.

A link to the program is included in the references [1]. The workshop had 15 registered participants from across the iFAST community.

Presentations from CERN, ISIS-II, and ESS detailed energy strategy, waste heat use, and general approach to sustainability and energy efficiency.

Presentations from PSI, Uppsala University, ESS, and Elettra highlighted examples of efficient and novel power source designs. All presentations showed impressive control and efficiency progress.

Throughout, interesting discussions regarding the material presented were held.

3 Summary of talks and discussions

3.1 ENERGY STRATEGY, SUSTAINABILITY

The rising energy costs poses a significant challenge for research organizations, impacting the operational duration of accelerator facilities. To counter this, many facilities are adopting a strategic approach, where you spread the risks with price volatility by own production, storage, price hedging, and as a last resort, selling of waste heat. This goes hand in hand with sustainability efforts since the most effective way to counter energy cost is to spend less. Presentations and discussions within this section highlighted this.

3.1.1 CERN summary from David Nisbet

At CERN, several energy efficiency initiatives are running. These are, among others:

- i) Heat recovered is injected into the heating system in a local community
- ii) Building within the CERN complexes are heated by recovered heat in various ways
- iii) Several improvements are discussed and implemented to improve LHC cryogenics efficiency (LHC cryogenics is a major part of CERN energy consumption)
- iv) In the East Area Experimental Complex, a project for efficiency was delivered 2021. The energy use was reduced from 10.85 GWh/y to 0.66 GWh/y by pulsed powering. At the same time water used went from 21900 cubic meters to 1337 cubic meters yearly
- v) For the North Area, all power converters are planned to be replaced until 2033. Optimisation and improvements are expected to yield up to 50% energy use reduction
- vi) FCC plans include plans for efficiency and energy storage to improve efficiency (novel topologies, capacitors, batteries, flywheels, fuel cells, and gravitational storage)
- vii) Overall, CERN has managed to increase luminosity in LHC experiments and lowering energy used by more than 95% since the first run

3.1.2 ESS Overall Energy Strategy Supply of Electricity and Heat/Cooling, from Kent Hedin

In ESS, several paths towards sustainability are employed. These include hedging and waste heat recovery. Future methods include own production via solar panels and/or gas turbines, energy storage to even out price volatility (within the FlexRICAN project), and power purchase agreements to limit open market exposure.

The main target is to have an active strategy. The energy cost should not be totally open to market price variations. Therefore, own production (PV panels), PPAs, energy storage, and price hedging will be components of any strategy during operations. Further, ESS was designed to facilitate sustainability (see next section).

3.1.3 Cooling and sustainability in ESS from Björn Eldvall

This presentation focused on some of the details of the heat recovery and the energy concepts, and what could be achieved now and in the future.

ESS was designed to allow heat recovery with three different temperature regions for the cooling water. This makes recovery more efficient, and ESS is already selling heat to the district heating

provider. One future goal is to have the highest cooling water to provide heat directly to the local grid – today heat pumps are required, with a penalty in efficiency.

At ESS, a Central Utility Building controls the temperatures and flows of the cooling water. No cooling tower is present, rather all excess heat is sold to the district grid.

Three temperature levels are employed: Low (around 10 degrees C); Medium (around 20 degrees C); and Warm (40 degrees C and upwards). This allows optimisation of the cooling flows depending on the use – warm cooling water is for example employed for the klystron collectors, and this water can reach temperatures of 65 degrees C or more. This is used to sell heat. The lower temperature circuits are employed via a local grid to heat the ESS premises. So, during operations, ESS will get all its heat from the facility itself.

3.1.4 Sustainability at ISIS-II by Hannah Wakeling

In this presentation the efforts to evaluate environmental impact for the future ISI-II facility were detailed.

ISIS-II is a spallation neutron and muon source, to be placed at RAL in UK, where the ISIS facility already operates for 40 years. ISIS-II is an upgrade to 1.2 GeV/2.4 MW power beam. Target date is 2040.

Various design options that have been considered were broadly presented. The methodology for environmental impact assessment was also presented. The focus is to find hot spots with large environmental impact. The design phase is really the ideal time to look at these considerations. Both construction and operations were considered. A grand total LCA is the goal. This obviously is a bit hard, since the expected lifetime is 60 years, and some assumptions on the carbon footprint of UK power supply are required.

Questions in the study include operation regime (DC/Pulsed DC); Systems approach (handle each large power use as a system); Priority setting (performance, reliability, obsolescence, lifetime, ...) Outside or in-house design. Work is ongoing, and the community is encouraged to advice and comment.

3.1.5 Discussions

There were good discussions about these subjects, especially when you go to the detail on how to ensure sustainability. It may look simple during the design phase, but when it is implemented, there may be issues that were not considered during the design phase. A good example is that ESS earlier considered using 80+ degrees C water for the hot circuit, something that was eventually not implemented for perceived safety concerns. This is now under re-evaluation since the need to lift the water via a heat pump is not really that efficient.

3.2 POWER CONVERTER DESIGNS

This part focused on novel concepts. Many interesting concepts were introduced and discussed.

3.2.1 The new Booster Dipole Power Supply for the Swiss Light Source by René Kunzi, PSI

The presentation detailed the concepts of these dipole supplies, where the specifications include very fast swing and dual voltage requirements. Very tight control of the waveforms is required.

To meet the specifications, the requirements were split in DC and AC parts and stacked PI controllers were employed. Very precise control was achieved by the concept.

Further, the lifetime of the converters could be greatly improved by addressing “power cycling”, where mechanical forces due to thermal cycling reduce the IGBT lifetime. New IGBT types and better thermal management helped improve this.

Finally, power consumption was reduced by changing the operation mode of the converters from continuous to “stop and go” (split in slow and fast cycles).

3.2.2 Power converters at ESS by Max Collins

For klystron modulators, high efficiency, low droop, and very limited pulse ripple are required. Especially the ripple is very hard to control. The ESS klystron modulators are built using an active front-end to control the charging of the capacitor banks. Standard components are used as much as possible. To achieve the high voltage required (-115 kV), six pulse transformers at 15-25 kV are used and the resulting pulse is formed by stacking them. The design is totally modular. The power is 660 kVA.

By interleaving the controls of each HV step, very low ripple is achieved (0.15%) at -115 kV.

The modulators are very cost-effective and smaller than other designs by a factor of 40%. ESS employs these modulators for all klystrons, both 352 MHz and 704 MHz – the design fits both klystron designs and the power allows driving two 352 MHz klystrons or four 704 MHz klystrons.

3.2.3 RF-power at Uppsala University by Dragos Dancila

Uppsala University operates a test stand where all ESS Spoke Cryomodules are tested. To this end, two tube-based RF sources were purchased, and they have been operated for ca 10 years now. In parallel, UU performs research on Solid State based amplifier solutions.

The footprint of power transistors is continuously shrinking, and RF sources that previously required a large instrument hall can now be constructed within the volume of a few electronics racks.

The presentation dealt with how the specifications for ESS could be achieved. These are 400 kW peak RF power, 5 to 10% duty. Several design options were shown, and some suggestions on how the challenges should be met. Target footprint is 4 m².

The proposed design is highly modular, employing as base a 1.6 kW transistor. All modules are carefully controlled and via combiner network and careful matching 100 kW output per rack can be achieved. Coaxial power splitters and combiners are employed here, and they have been built and tested successfully. For the final combination 4x100 kW to 400 kW a concept design exists.

3.2.4 ESS tetrode-based RF spoke power amplifiers by Yogi Rutambhara

At ESS the Spoke linac (26 dual spoke cavities) is powered by Tetrode-tube based RF stations. The presentation focused on how these works and experiences from installing and commissioning the stations.

The tubes have received a lot of attention since many trips were perceived to originate from the Tetrodes. However, many other sources of trips are present and these, together with the tubes, were outlined and discussed in the presentation. Sources of trips include switches, internal power converters, cracks on tubes, dirt in coax lines, etc.

The extensive debugging and improvement of the stations was also highlighted.

After installation and commissioning, the Spoke RF Power Stations are expected to work well.

3.2.5 From ESS to Elettra 2.0: Corrector, Multipolar and Dipole Power Converters by Marco Cautero

This presentation focused on Magnet Power Converters for Elettra 2.0 (Elettra upgrade). Since Elettra was partner to ESS and delivered magnet power converters to ESS, the experiences from this project were very useful for the design of magnet power converters for the Elettra upgrade. Here, footprint, availability, and sustainability were key concerns.

The result was that only 3 different types of converters were required for the entire Elettra machine. Standardization was also employed.

The designs yielded very impressive results for current ripple, stability, and efficiency. For example, the current ripple was 20 times better than the specifications.

In all, the project was very successful.

3.3 DISCUSSIONS

For this part of the workshop the discussions focused mostly on the specifics of each design, and how it was important.

4 Workshop Highlights

The workshop showed that all facilities can make big steps towards sustainability. This is true in the design and construction phase for newer facilities and during operation and upgrades. For newer facilities it can be planned into the concept and design. For older facilities it can be done by carefully designing how operations are made, and by taking sustainability into account when equipment is replaced or when new capabilities are introduced.

It was also clear that what seems straightforward at the planning stage may be a lot less so during the actual construction and commissioning of a facility.

The workshop also highlighted an impressive selection of novel high-performance power converter designs.

5 References

- [1] “iFAST Workshop on Efficient Electrical Power Converters for Accelerator Applications,” ESS Indico (Indico). Available: <https://indico.ess.eu/event/3396> (password “iFast2024”)